

A new solid sorbent system for rapid monitoring of nicotine

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A new solid sorbent system is developed for the monitoring of nicotine in the environment. The lower limit of detection is 0.05 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of nicotine for the reagent papers and indicator tubes. The lower limit of determination by spectrophotometric procedure is 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of air. The preparation of indicator tubes, test papers and their applications for the detection and determination of nicotine in environmental tobacco smoke (ETS), mainstream smoke (MS), side stream smoke (SS) and biological samples is described in this paper.

The detection/determination of nicotine is of particular importance to tobacco industry and in the area of toxicology. Various analytical methods including TLC, GC, HPLC, GC-MS, AAS, electrophoresis-MS, inhibition biosensor, PXR, circular dichroism spectropolarimetry have been reported for its determination¹. Most of the methods reported on colorimetric determination of nicotine are based on cleavage of the pyridine ring with cyanogen bromide or chloride and condensation of the resulting compound with *p*-aminobenzoic acid, 2-naphthylamine or diethylthio-barbituric acid. These methods involve prolonged extraction procedure prior to the determination of nicotine and uses highly toxic reagent².

The present method, which is based on dehydrogenation of nicotine using platinum black and further its reaction with vaniline and phosphoric acid to give red coloured condensed product was reported earlier³. The same reagent system has been applied for the preparation of indicator tubes and test papers. The method was successfully applied to the detection/determination of nicotine in tobacco smoke and biological samples. The present method is found to be more simple, stable and selective.

Results and discussion

The red compound formed in the indicator tubes as well in the test papers was extracted in water and exhibited maximum absorbance at 500 nm. As low as 0.05 μg of nicotine could be detected by the method. The molar absorptivity of the coloured system is $6.2 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Linear absorbance values were obtained up to 2 ppm of nicotine which is sufficient for all practical purposes. Colour intensities obtained at constant flow rate could satisfactorily be

compared. Colour development did not occur under extremely dry conditions. In fact it was found that certain amount of humidity was always necessary and was maintained by adding a few drops of calcium chloride to the reagent solution. It was found that the absorption of nicotine was complete in the first impinger. Methanolic sodium hydroxide was found to be highly efficient (99–100%) in the absorption of the nicotine. The flow rate was maintained at 1 L/min. Effect of other gaseous pollutants normally present in the environment was studied. It was found that these gaseous pollutants did not interfere up to 100 ppm in colour development.

The indicator tubes and reagent papers prepared as described were stable up to ~6 months when kept in closed bottles in a desiccator. The colour formed was stable for 1 month. The test papers and indicator gave reproducible results under optimum conditions.

The proposed sorbent system is simple, sensitive and stable. The colour development is very rapid in comparison to other reported methods using reagents – diethylthio-barbituric acid (λ_{max} 538 nm, 10 μg), potassium iodide with starch (λ_{max} 580 nm, 3.7–29.6 mg)⁴. The lower limit of detection is 0.05 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and results obtained are reproducible.

Experimental

Apparatus : A Carl-Zeiss spekol with 10 mm matched silica cells and a Systronics 108 ultraviolet-visible digital spectrophotometer was used for all spectrophotometric measurements, 35 ml midget impingers and (PIMCO) calibrated rotameters were used for air sampling.

Note

Reagents : All chemical used were of AnalaR grade unless stated otherwise doubly distilled deionized water was used throughout.

Nicotine : This was extracted from tobacco leaves and standardized spectroscopically⁴.

Absorbing solution : \ 0.01 mol/L sodium hydroxide solution in 10% methanol was used.

Preparation of reagent : 0.5 g of vanillin was dissolved in 99 ml of 85% phosphoric acid. Then 1 ml of 10% calcium chloride (humectant) was added and stirred with a glass rod. This reagent was used for the preparation of indicator tubes and test papers.

Preparation of indicator tubes : Well cleaned and dried graduated glass tube size 6 × 0.5 cm I.D. were taken and plugged with glass wool ~2 cm. Then the dried reagent impregnated cellulose fibre was filled to another ~2 cm length and the remaining part of the tube was filled with glass wool. The both ends of tubes were sealed. These tubes were then kept in a desiccator.

Preparation of the test papers : Whatman filter paper no. 1 was cut into strips of size 5 × 2 cm and dipped in the reagent solution. Then the strips were taken out and dried for 1 h in a snap action thermostat maintained at ~40°C.

Procedure for dehydrogenation of nicotine : Nicotine was dehydrogenated using platinum black³. A small quantity of the nicotine is mixed with a quantity of the platinum-black and heated in a vessel to 170°C for 1.5 h, taking care to prevent the nicotine from evaporating off. After the sample is cooled, 5 ml of distilled water was added and the whole is filtered. The filtrate (dehydrogenated nicotine) was then evaporated and vapours were generated in a hood⁵. Prior to estimation the sealed ends of the indicator tube were cut and one end of it was connected to a source of suction through which dehydrogenated nicotine vapours generated in a hood was drawn. The intensity of the colour and length of stain developed were proportional to the concentration of nicotine, which was estimated by comparing the colour with that of standards treated similarly. Alternatively the coloured substance was extracted in 5 ml of water and the absorbance was measured at 500 nm. The reagent papers were exposed to dehydrogenated nicotine vapours generated in a hood where these turned red. The intensity of colour developed was proportional to the concentration of nicotine. Quantitative evaluation was made by extracting the dye with 5 ml of water and measuring the absorbance at 500 nm.

Applications :

Determination of nicotine in tobacco smoke : Tobacco smoke was drawn through 10 ml of absorbing solution contained in two midget impingers connected in series to a source of suction a flow rate of 1 L/min. After sampling an aliquot was taken from the first impinger, suitably diluted with water, dehydrogenated and evaporated in a hood and drawn through the tube at a flow rate of 1 L/min for 10 min. A red colour stain in a indicator tube indicated the presence of nicotine in tobacco smoke (Table 1).

Table 1. Determination of nicotine in tobacco smoke

Sample		Nicotine found ^a (µg)	
		Proposed method	Reported method ²
tobacco smoke			
Environmental	A	1.56	1.42
tobacco smoke (ETS)	B	1.89	1.78
	C	1.95	1.62
	D	1.78	1.59
Mainstream smoke	A	1.43	1.32
(MS)	B	1.28	1.12
	C	1.46	1.38
	D	1.32	1.21
Sidestream smoke	A	1.12	1.02
(SS)	B	1.21	1.15
	C	1.05	0.96
	D	1.18	0.98

^aMean of three replicate analyses.

Determination of nicotine in blood urine and mother's milk : For assessing the applicability of the method to biological samples blood, urine and milk samples were obtained from smokers and nonsmokers. A 1 ml aliquot of blood/serum, urine or milk sample was taken and deproteinized by adding 2 ml of 1% trichloroacetic acid⁶. After 25 min the mixture was centrifuged and the supernatant solution was transferred into a 25 ml calibrated tube, dehydrogenated and evaporated in a hood. Vapours were then drawn through the tube and analysed as described above (Table 2).

Table 2. Determination of nicotine in biological samples

Sample ^a		Nicotine found ^b (µg)	
		Proposed method	Reported method ²
Blood/Serum	A ^c	1.82	1.65
	B ^c	1.65	1.89
	C ^d	1.32	1.12
	D ^d	1.26	0.98
Urine	A ^c	0.95	0.82
	B ^c	0.83	0.75
	C ^d	0.47	0.28
	D ^d	0.52	0.41
Mothers milk	A ^c	0.87	0.62
	B ^c	0.92	0.81
	C ^d	0.45	0.34
	D ^d	0.32	0.21

^a A 1 ml volume was taken in each instance.

^b Mean of three replicate analyses.

^c Samples A and B were taken from smokers.

^d Samples C and D were taken from nonsmokers.

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